

Understanding Teachers' Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes Using an Explanatory Sequential Approach

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Abstract. This study determined the influence of learner-centered pedagogical skills on students' knowledge acquisition processes. An explanatory sequential mixed method was employed to obtain data from 175 elementary school teachers across five public schools in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. Meanwhile, 17 participants were chosen from the quantitative respondents to participate in the IDI and FGD. Results revealed that learner-centered pedagogical skills were moderately extensive, while students' knowledge acquisition processes were rated as extensive. In addition, regression analysis indicated that learner-centered pedagogical skills regarding online connections and student self-perception significantly influenced the students' knowledge acquisition processes. Results from the thematic analysis of qualitative data confirmed the moderately extensive teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills, extensive students' knowledge acquisition processes, and the significant influence of teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills on the students' knowledge acquisition processes. With this confirmation, it was possible to conclude that there was substantial evidence that teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills were one of the reasons students' knowledge acquisition processes were extensive, as demonstrated by the regression model. Lastly, connecting-merging-confirmation surfaced as the nature of data integration in which qualitative results explain the quantitative results of the study.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management
2. learner-centered pedagogical skills
3. knowledge acquisition processes
4. mixed-method approach

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1. Introduction

Understanding the knowledge acquisition processes of students in academic institutions is essential because it may provide a glimpse of how the instructions and academic practices are going on in the university. As such, it could be used as a powerful tool by teachers and academic supervisors to design some effective pedagogical techniques to maximize learners' learning experiences. The data on students' knowledge acquisition processes in the context of technology and livelihood education provides information on what learners are doing. The data is more significant for managing institutions, learners, and academic programs. Rather than work from assumptions or partial anecdotal reports about learner's activities, institutions

can make decisions based on more objective information. Information about students' activities would provide institutions with valuable information for policy enhancement to become more responsive to students' needs. Waugh (2001) highlighted that knowledge acquisition processes are a helpful element that could contribute to meaningful engagement throughout the learning environment. According to Albalade et al. (2018), students actively engaged in knowledge acquisition processes efficiently use cognitive and metacognitive strategies. Hubert (2017) highlighted that engaged students can control various mental strategies for better cognitive performance, enhanced ability to attend to things in a selective and focused way, concentrate over some time, quickly learn new information and skills, determine strategies for actions, easily comprehend scientific language and can retain information and manipulate it to solve complex scientific problems. Moreover, Tasgin and Tunc (2018) emphasize that learners with high learning motivation conduct themselves in ways that maximize acquisition and knowledge. Meanwhile, studies indicated that the knowledge acquisition skills of the students are linked to teachers' abilities and skills. For instance, Bosman and Schulze (2018) concluded that students' knowledge acquisition processes are affected by the learner-centered pedagogical skills of teachers. As defined by Metin (2011), learner-centered pedagogical skills of the teachers are the measurement of teachers' skills, performance, and beliefs that reflect real-world situations and require the students to develop their original responses explaining the processes followed to achieve those results. In line with this, Yu (2014) pointed out that learner-centered teaching skills help engage learners in real-world tasks rather than multiple-choice tests and evaluate them according to criteria critical for actual performance in a field of work. Likewise, Naimnule and Corebima (2018) showed that knowledge-processing skills are essential for successful learning because they enable individuals to direct their cognitive skills to a higher level. On a different view, the decreased extent of knowledge acquisition processes among learners at the elementary school level remains an unresolved dilemma among educational institutions worldwide. For instance, Ali (2018) reported that despite the interventions and research on poor or fair learners' knowledge acquisition processes, it remained a problem for educators worldwide. In developed countries, Bango and Mahesar (2018) mentioned that learners with poor satisfaction in learning continue to be very passive in classroom activities, especially in interactions, because it has been observed that most of the learners, ages 8-12 years old, are taking more time on the virtual world rather than studying their notes. Similarly, Sikhwari (2014) reports that learners in higher education who possess low levels of learners' knowledge acquisition processes are seldom engaged in school activities. This is because learners cannot cope with the complexity of the subjects when they enter the elementary school level. Much of the research on the knowledge acquisition processes of students involved tertiary level and utilized a quantitative approach. The researcher has not yet found any study utilizing a method research design. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Carmen District, Davao del Norte, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used a sequential explanatory research design to better understand the learners' knowledge acquisition processes about teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills in the context of technology and livelihood education, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding using mixed method design in students' knowledge acquisition processes. The results of this study may be of interest to other researchers as

they could provide valuable knowledge for their research.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—This section covers the relevant literature on learner-centered pedagogical skills, student self-perception, online learning experiences, and knowledge acquisition processes, drawing from various books, journals, and electronic sources.

1.1.1. Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills—Learner-centered pedagogical skills emphasize real-world applications that encourage student engagement through practical performance and interactive tasks. Metin (2011) and Yu (2014) emphasize that effective teaching involves engaging students in meaningful, authentic tasks, which develop both oral and written skills through discussions, experiments, and projects. Amin et al. (2013), Jalbani (2014), and Alsafi (2011) further argue that aligning teaching strategies with students' learning styles increases motivation and performance. Zelle et al. (2015) and Dörnyei and Ushioda (2011) suggest that such strategies foster autonomy and motivation in learners.

1.1.2. Online Learning and Technology Integration—Technology in education enhances learning by facilitating self-managed, interactive experiences. Studies by Hosseini and Kamal (2012), Baran et al. (2011), and Chaboualapha and Islam (2012) highlight the benefits of ICT, including troubleshooting, managing digital resources, and optimizing educational tools. Internet-based learning fosters collaboration, critical thinking, and independence among students (Liao Hsieh, 2012; Ivwighreghweta Igere, 2014). However, challenges such as technical difficulties and information overload persist.

1.1.3. Student Self-Perception and Engagement—Student engagement, critical to learning, is shaped by their perception of their abilities and classroom experiences. Fredricks (2014) and Tang (2013) highlight that a student-centered approach enhances collaboration, com-

munication, and self-efficacy. Cooperative learning environments promote active participation and meaningful dialogue, leading to deeper understanding and retention (Reino, 2012; Akaba, 2014; Tian, 2011).

1.1.4. Knowledge Acquisition Processes—Effective knowledge acquisition involves various instructional strategies that accommodate different learning styles and preferences. Waugh (2001) defines these processes as activities that enhance learning quality by stimulating critical thinking and problem-solving. Studies by Velki (2011), Brophy (2010), and Wegner et al. (2014) suggest that learner-centered approaches improve students' motivation, engagement, and knowledge retention. Research by Guido and Dela Cruz (2011), Akomolafe and Adesua (2015), and Abdulwahab et al. (2016) further supports the use of cooperative and interactive learning strategies to boost academic achievement.

1.1.5. Classroom Management and Instructional Delivery—Effective instructional delivery and classroom management strategies, such as those described by Nevid (2011) and Llego (2017), focus on creating engaging, student-centered learning environments. Techniques like cooperative learning and problem-based learning encourage active involvement and higher-order thinking skills. Engagement in schoolwork is linked to motivation and persistence, which is crucial for academic success, particularly in challenging subjects like mathematics and science (Ingram, 2014; Benken et al., 2015; Albalate et al., 2018).

1.2. Synthesis—Therefore, this portion of the paper provides the researcher with the discussions of literature and the results of other research to which the present study is related or has some bearing and similarity. More so, the literature showed that teachers' learner-centered teaching skills, as conceptualized by Metin (2011) measured in terms of online connections, student self-perception, experience with

online courses, and instructor evaluation, while knowledge acquisition processes as proposed by Waugh (2001) is measured in terms of mastery of the lesson, communication, instructional delivery, and student engagement.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework— A pragmatic paradigm was applied in this study. It aims to identify the problem and view it within its broadest context. As a pragmatist, the researcher adheres to a pragmatic worldview in which the creation of individual realities is treated as a derivative of varying personal experiences and ideas encountered and not of an absolute default (Maddux Donnett, 2015). Through pragmatic exploration, an optimum answer was provided, as facts and accuracy may differ cross-wise between and among people, places, and periods. Furthermore, the researcher, like Terrell (2012), did not focus on issues and approaches by using only one method; rather, she embraced the pragmatic paradigm, which involves mixing data collection methods and data analysis procedures within the research processes (Creswell, 2013). The study's primary concern is the emphasis on initiatives that have meaningful consequences in solving learning issues, particularly desire for academic recognition among students in technology and livelihood education. Furthermore, this pragmatic approach is intended to design the research process, including all phases necessary for the theoretical underpinning of data collection and analysis. Hence, it can be deduced from the above that the philosophical worldview of things is vital to the meaning of research methodology. The study is anchored on Wegner et al.'s (2014) proposition that students become more active and engaged in the learning process and learn better when their teachers use different teaching strategies in the classroom. Good teaching quality and teachers' use of it in the classroom increase students' satisfaction. Students always remember what they did, not what they memorized. When students actively

participate in the learning process, knowledge is not just being transferred but meaningfully constructed by the learner. In support, Zakaria and Iksan (2012) proposed that effective strategies allow students to exchange resources, question each other's conclusions, and defend their ideas, which requires students to use higher-order thinking. Effective teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills also allow students to practice communicating scientific ideas. Effective teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills benefit students in multiple ways, resulting in more meaningful learning connections. The study consists of two variables. The independent variable was the TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills or the measurement of teachers' skills, performance, and beliefs that reflect real-world situations and require the students to develop original responses explaining the processes followed to achieve those results. According to Metin (2011), Learner-centered pedagogical skills were online connections or the instructiveness on online learning, student self-perception or the ability to encourage students to learn and be involved in the educative process, experience with online courses or the student's ability to monitor their phase of learning through the use of online connections, and instructor evaluation or the teachers' attitude on a performance assessment tool that was being used in the class. The study's dependent variable was students' knowledge acquisition processes or the factor contributed by the quality of learning and being responsible for learning. The measures of students' knowledge acquisition processes, according to Waugh (2011) are mastery of the lesson or the student's ability to exert the best effort to reach the academic standards that they set for themselves, communication or the process of communicating techniques essential for acquiring, processing, storing, and recalling information in a certain situation, instructional delivery or the instructional activities that were carried out in the instructional

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

process and which instructional methods and techniques that were employed in the process, and student engagement or the student's involvement in the scientific activity of the classroom and their commitment to learning.

1.4. Purpose of the Study—This study addressed the influence of TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills on the students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. An explanatory sequential mixed methods design was used, and it involved collecting qualitative data after quantitative results to explain or follow up on the quantitative results in more depth. In the quantitative phase of the study, primary data was collected

from the elementary school teachers in Carmen District in Davao City regarding the TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes. The qualitative phase was conducted to establish the authenticity of the regression model obtained from the quantitative results.

1.5. Research Questions—The research questions underlying the investigation in this study were as follows:

- (1) What are the standpoints of the participants on the salient points of the results on the extent of TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills in Carmen District, Davao del Norte?
- (2) What are the standpoints of the participants on the salient points of the results on the extent of students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte?
- (3) What are the standpoints of the participants on the salient points of the results on the influence of TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills on students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte?
- (4) How do the qualitative results explain the quantitative results of the study?

1.6. Hypotheses—The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance: H01: TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical

skills do not have a significant influence on students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. This mas-

ter's thesis would benefit individuals in different sectors: Department of Education. This may serve as the basis for the Department of Education to formulate policies that may improve educational practices about teachers' learner-centered teaching skills and learners' knowledge acquisition processes. The findings bridge the methodological divide in teaching practices research by attempting to understand the teachers' learner-centered pedagogical and knowledge processing skills toward learners' knowledge acquisition processes. Teachers. The findings are essential to the teaching profession because they might suggest future evidence-based interventions that can be implemented regarding the importance of analyzing teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills that may be very helpful to the student's knowledge acquisition processes by aiding them to become more focused and attentive students. Students. Students would benefit from the findings of this study because they may help them understand the importance of identifying the factors that may enhance their knowledge-acquisition processes. Through the development of teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills and learners' knowledge processing skills, they could increase their capabilities and strengths, followed by enhancing the effectiveness of their learning experience. This may guide learners to plan or modify their learning methods parallel to their learning preferences. Future Researchers. The findings were essential to future researchers because they might suggest future evidence-based interventions that can be implemented regarding the importance of developing aspects of teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes. These could be very helpful to students' learning achievement by aiding them in becoming more focused and attentive. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined conceptually and operationally: Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills. This study refers to the independent variable being described in terms of online connections, student self-perception, experience with online courses, and instructor evaluation. Knowledge Acquisition Processes. This study refers to the dependent variable being described in terms of the following indicators: mastery of the lesson, communication, instructional delivery, and classroom engagement.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to proofread this work during its preparation meticulously. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed mixed methods, specifically explanatory sequential research design. This is an evolving research technique that promotes the systematic synthesis or mixing of quantitative and qualitative data within a single study or ongoing investigation or inquiry (Creswell, 2013). This method collects and

analyzes both quantitative and qualitative data and integrates data during data collection, analysis, and discussion. This method uses procedures that implement quantitative and qualitative components concurrently (Creswell, 2017). According to West (2012), in sequential explanatory design, the qualitative data helps explain or build on the initial quantitative results in the explanatory sequential method. The explanatory sequential approach is a two-phase mixed methods design that explains and enriches the quantitative findings; thus, it elaborates the quantitative results by collecting qualitative data from participants chosen from the respondents of the quantitative phase. Sometimes, there are insufficient arguments that quantitative or qualitative may not be resolved by it, and sometimes each provides different pictures (Creswell, 2017). In the quantitative phase, the researcher specifically used the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts and information related to the study. descriptive-correlational research, according to Myers and Well (2013), examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause and effect relationships between variables. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to perform an experiment in a controlled set-up. In this study, the researcher looked into the relationship between two variables— teachers’ learner-centered pedagogical skills and students’ knowledge acquisition processes. In the qualitative phase, the researcher used a phenomenological approach. A phenomenological study describes the common meaning for several individuals of their lived experiences of a concept or phenomenon and focuses on the commonality of their lived experiences (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event,

situation, or experience. Phenomenology is the most appropriate approach to use because the researcher wants to understand the lived experiences of teachers in Carmen District, Davao del norte in relation to teachers’ learner-centered pedagogical skills and students’ knowledge acquisition processes (Creswell, 2017). Moreover, the quantitative data based on the survey questionnaires on teachers’ learner-centered pedagogical skills and students’ knowledge acquisition processes was first collected and followed by the qualitative data based on the focus group discussion (FGD) and in-depth interview (IDI). This means a more dynamic and absolute understanding is possible than the use of only one data source alone (Creswell, 2013). Likewise, this method was used to compare, confirm, cross-validate, or corroborate findings, equally prioritizing the quantitative method. The researcher analyzed the survey data quantitatively and the FGD and IDI qualitatively to determine if the qualitative findings elaborated the quantitative findings (Creswell, 2013). Hence, this design was appropriate to use purposely to supplement one method with the strengths of another (Creswell, 2013). Specifically, the quantitative component involved descriptive and correlational approaches.

2.2. Research Respondents—Quantitative Strand. The participants of the quantitative phase were the 175 teachers in the selected public elementary schools in Carmen District in Davao del Norte who have been teaching in the selected schools for three years. The researcher employed cluster sampling in selecting the participants from purposively selected elementary schools in Carmen District in Davao del Norte. According to Salkind (2020), cluster sampling was defined as a type of probability sampling that was often used to study large populations, particularly those that are widely geographically dispersed. Adding on, cluster sampling was a sampling plan used when mutually homogeneous yet internally heterogeneous groupings

are evident in a statistical population (Thomas, 2021). The advantage of this method was often more economical or more practical than stratified sampling or simple random sampling. So, it was usually used when a researcher cannot get information about the population as a whole, but they could get information about the clusters. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the teacher participants of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose male and female participants who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those full-time teachers who have been teaching for at least three years in the public elementary schools whose school principals have been designated with the position for at least three years, and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem base on the research questions and thus it did not consider the rank status and performance ratings of the teachers.

2.3. *Qualitative Strand*—In the qualitative phase, the researcher purposively selected 10 public elementary school teachers for the IDI and 7 public school elementary school teachers for the FGD. A total of 17 public elementary school teachers were invited as participants. Inclusion criteria that were used are as follows: have been teaching for at least three years in the public elementary schools. It was also considered that the numbers of male and female are well represented. As Crouch and McKenzie (2006), postulated that for FGD, the recommended sample size is seven to eight participants since a group of more than 10 participants for in-depth interview is difficult to

The second part of the instrument concerns the students' knowledge acquisition processes, which consist of statements that were divided into indicators of mastery of the lesson, commu-

control and limits each person's opportunity to share insights and observations. A focus group with less than 10 participants is easier to recruit and host which can also be comfortable for the participants. Moreover, purposive sampling was apt for the qualitative participant selection of this study because, according to Daymon and Holloway (2011), it is a technique wherein a sample was chosen based on their particular features or characteristics, which enables detailed exploration and understanding of the constructs under the study and research questions. As denoted by Miles et al. (2014), purposive sampling was well suited to in-depth qualitative studies.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—Two sets of instruments were used in this study; one for the quantitative phase and one for the qualitative phase. These questionnaires were subjected to content validity by a panel of experts and underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability. The comments, corrections, and suggestions given by the experts were incorporated in the final revisions of the questionnaires. Quantitative Phase. In the quantitative phase, the researcher used the instrument concerned with TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills, which are composed of that was divided among the domains, namely: online connections, student self-perception, experience with online courses, and instructor evaluation. The reliability of the scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.954, described as excellent and interpreted as very reliable. As a guide in determining the extent of TLE teachers' learner-centered teaching skills, the researcher used the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below.

nication, instructional delivery, and classroom engagement. The reliability of the scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.976, described as excellent and interpreted as very re-

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The learner-centered pedagogical skills of TLE teachers are always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The learner-centered pedagogical skills of TLE teachers are oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learner-centered pedagogical skills of TLE teachers are sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The learner-centered pedagogical skills of TLE teachers are seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The learner-centered pedagogical skills of TLE teachers are never observed.

liable. As a guide in determining the extent of the knowledge acquisition processes of the learners, the researcher used a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below.

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The students' knowledge acquisition processes are always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The students' knowledge acquisition processes are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The students' knowledge acquisition processes are sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The students' knowledge acquisition processes are seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The students' knowledge acquisition processes are never manifested.

Qualitative Phase. The researcher conducted an IDI and FGD with a total of 17 elementary school teachers using a semi-structured interview. The use of the semi-structured approach was essential to discover new themes that emerged during the interview. As described by Bryman and Bell (2011), is flexible and less rigid than structured. The researcher made an interview guide composed of open-ended questions to probe the participants' lived experiences

with regard to TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes. Also, the researcher probed how these experiences shape their beliefs, attitudes, and commitment toward teaching. This interview guide had undergone content validation by three experts in the field of education. Their comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated in the final revisions of the questionnaires.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire.

2.6. *Quantitative Phase*—Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school's division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the approval to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. More so, the respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

For the qualitative data collection, IDI and FGD were conducted to gather the lived experiences of the participants with regard to TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes after the invited participants have emailed back the signed ICF. Regarding the conduct of the IDI and FGD, the researcher reflected in the ICF that the process had to be recorded. Only those invited participants who were able to email back their signed ICF were scheduled to join the IDI

and FGD. Also, the researcher made sure that her time schedule was most convenient with the participants. Using the validated open-ended questionnaire, she had to limit the IDI and FGD sessions to 30 to 40 minutes. In addition, she thoroughly discussed the ethical considerations with the participants. Also, the participants' perspectives on the phenomenon of interest were revealed according to how they viewed it, not as the researcher viewed it. Also, since the interview involved a personal interaction where cooperation was essential (Creswell, 2013), the researcher who acted as the interviewer saw to it that she had a good rapport with the interviewees by using a non-threatening stance during the IDI. Likewise, for the FGD, the researcher sent an email or text through messenger to confirm the availability of the participants who signed up to join the FGD at the time scheduled for the FGD Google Meet session. An invite was sent through email at least two days before the scheduled FGD session. The researcher acted as the facilitator during the FGD and stimulated the discussion or brainstorming through sensibly chosen guide statements, which were prepared beforehand and validated by a panel of experts. Participants in the FGD were informed prior to submission of signed ICF and they were informed that the whole session was going to be recorded.

2.7. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—To establish the study's trustworthiness, the researcher followed the four proposed criteria for evaluating interpretive research work by Lincoln and Guba (1985): credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. This study's trustworthiness was addressed through a thorough data collection by survey and in-depth interview, supported by FGD for triangulation. Credibility. To ensure the credibility of this study, the researcher adopted a well-established research method. The researcher recognized the importance of incorporating correct operational measures for the concept that was being

studied. Credibility was achieved by ensuring that the source of the data was credible. The researcher also ensured the honesty of the participants by giving them a chance to refuse to participate in the study. Also, the researcher ensured the quality of this study by carefully adhering to the protocols set by the Rizal Memorial Colleges Graduate School; the process flow in data collection, data analysis, and data integration were carefully reviewed, ensuring quality and dependability. Transferability. The researcher addressed transferability by providing readers with evidence that the research findings could be applicable to other contexts, situations, times, and populations. Transferability is concerned with the extent to which the findings of the study can be applied to other situations (Creswell, 2013). The readers had to note the specific details of the specific situations and methods to compare them to a similar situation familiar to them. Dependability. To address dependability issue more directly, the researcher made sure that the process within the study was discussed in detail, thereby enabling future researchers to repeat the work, if not necessarily to gain the same results or findings of the study. In order for the readers to gain a thorough understanding of the methods and their effectiveness, the researcher included sections such as the research design and its implementation, described what was planned and how they were executed on a strategic level. The researcher described the operational detail of data collection, addressed the details of what has to be done in the field; and provided reflective appraisal of the project, evaluated the appropriateness of the process of the inquiry that was being undertaken. With the guidance of her mentor and evaluation of the expert panelists, all activities were done properly; as a result, stakeholders and the readers can be assured of the study's dependability. Confirmability. To safeguard the accuracy of the transcription and initial interpretation of the data, IDIs and FGD were

recorded and the transcriptions were subjected to the participants' responses review. The process included in Creswell (2017), steps and procedures in analyzing qualitative data known as the last stage in validating the accuracy of the information; through this method, the researcher assured confirmability of the study's findings (Creswell, 2017). As such, the researcher used an audit trail of raw data, analysis notes, process notes, personal notes, and preliminary developmental information to achieve confirmability. In other words, the researcher's findings were derived from the survey responses, and narratives of the participants in the IDI and FGD.

2.8. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study and given ample explanations so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refuse to participate, the researcher does not force them to. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission from the respondents was secured. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the students' knowledge acquisition processes in relation to TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills and may contribute to their enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The

study's respondents were teachers, so they were not considered vulnerable since all of them were of legal age, and they were not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey would be set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the data on the survey. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed of all the survey questionnaires and deleted the data results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study as well as the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. The respondents, without restrictions, were able to ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide that were used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents of the study. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the

researcher ensured the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study—anybody who fits the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier, and these were sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication about the research was done honestly and fairly. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher properly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents supporting the data analysis were included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study's results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that any other factor, like the conflict of interest, did not influence the respondents' responses. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating

schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the study's success; the Division of Davao del Norte was given a furnished copy of the research results so it could be accessed by the respondents and be used for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials that were ample and available during the study, which was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding the ratings of the respondents properly during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every phase of research, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared back with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.9. Data Analysis—Quantitative Phase The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes. Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the influence of TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills on the students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte.

Qualitative Strand The data from the IDI

and FGD were analyzed using thematic analysis. The interview was recorded so that the data and notes obtained could be analyzed to determine the emerging codes and themes. This method emphasizes pinpointing, examining, and recording patterns or themes within data. Themes were patterns across data sets that were important to describe a phenomenon and were associated with a specific research question (Mertens, 2018). In the thematic analysis, the researcher first read and re-read the transcripts to become familiar with the data. The data were organized in order to generate initial codes. Codes reduced ideas into smaller chunks of meaning. Codes were examined and grouped according to themes. Themes were formed, reviewed, modified, and developed. The themes were coherent and distinctive from each other. Lastly, the themes were defined to identify their meaning (Creswell, 2017).

2.10. Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures—A sequential collection of quantitative and qualitative components was employed in this study. However, the data integration happens during the analysis and interpretation phase. **Sequence.** A sequential-explanatory mixed-method design was used in this study. This means that the data gathered in the quantitative strand was further verified in the qualitative strand to explain the salient results of the survey. For the quantitative strand, the researcher collected the data through adapted questionnaires and interviews of the teachers in Carmen District schools in Davao del Norte with a validated interview guide for the qualitative phase. This means that the survey and interview were conducted separately and simultaneously. The qualitative data verified the quantitative data for cross-validation or confirmation of findings. With this method, the qualitative results determine the depth of the study's quantitative findings. **Emphasis.** The quantitative data were given more emphasis in the study because they used empirical tools and provided substantive

support for the qualitative findings. The findings were integrated during the interpretation phase of the study. The sequential-explanatory design framework shows two strands, with the data collection and analysis from the quantitative and qualitative strands. By mixing quantitative and qualitative research and data, the researcher gained an in-depth understanding after corroboration while offsetting the weaknesses inherent in using each approach. Mixing Procedures. The design required a substantial time to complete all data collection given the two separate phases. The main purpose of mixing quantitative and qualitative data is for the qualitative data to help explain the quantitative data. Thus, quantitative and qualitative data were connected. Mixed methodologies were observed in formulating the purpose, research questions, and integration of data in the findings and interpretation of the study. A data integration technique was applied to establish either the complementation of quantitative and qualitative data or the sequential connection between these data sets. The qualitative data either confirms or contrasts the quantitative findings. Neither of these citations of the previous studies explained the results. In addition, the specific research questions of the study served as a guide in interpreting the results. The mixing was done to understand better the influence of TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills on the students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. It was shown in Figure 2, the systematic procedure of the study. It demonstrates the use of a sequential-explanatory mixed methods design, where quantitative and qualitative data were cor-

roborated to determine the influence of TLE teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills on the students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. Then, after giving adequate time, the responses to the survey questionnaires were conducted, which were encoded and analyzed. Concurrently, IDI and FGD were conducted in the selected public schools. In the quantitative strand, the participants' responses to the validated survey questionnaire were analyzed using computer applications, and the answers were numeric data as the output. In addition, appropriate statistical tools, including mean and linear regression analysis, were used to analyze the quantitative data. After analysis, the data was presented according to the sequence of the research problems. In the qualitative data strand, the researcher purposefully selected the participants for the IDI and FGD. The IDI and FGD schedules were set at the participants' convenience. Every detail of the responses was taken into consideration, but those that were not relevant to the study were not reflected. In addition, the interview proceedings were recorded with the participant's consent. Thematic analysis was employed, consisting of six phases. The researcher started by transcribing, reading, and re-reading the data, and then initial codes or features of the data were created. The next phase was searching for the themes and collating the codes. As to the integration of the quantitative and qualitative results phases, the researcher interpreted and explained the quantitative and qualitative results to arrive at a very substantial discussion, implications, and recommendations.

3. Results and Discussion

This reflects the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings. Specifically, this chapter reveals both quantitative and qualitative data relevant to address the research questions formulated in Chapter 1. The tabulated quantitative and qualitative findings are presented in the Tables 1-15. The nature of data integration that exists between quantitative and qualitative results is shown in

Table 16

3.1. *Teachers' Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills*—Table 1 shows the summary on the extent of teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. As shown in the table, teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills obtained an overall mean score 3.26 which was described as moderately extensive. Moreover, the results on the table show that teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills in terms of students' self-perception acquired the highest mean score of 3.47 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. Meanwhile, teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills in terms of online connections acquired the lowest mean score of 3.26 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. The result denotes that the measurement of teacher's skills, performance and beliefs that reflect real-world situations and require the students to develop their original responses explaining the processes

followed in order to achieve those results is sometimes observed among the teachers in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. The result agrees with the view of Yu (2014) that the best quality of teaching help engaged students in real-world tasks rather than multiple-choice tests, and evaluate them according to criteria that are important for actual performance in a field of work. In addition, the result also agrees with the view of Shehadeh (2012) that good teaching quality allows students to accomplish approximations of real-life authentic tasks, usually using the productive skills of speaking or writing but also using reading or writing or combining skills. In short, those skills involve written and oral production, oral interactive activities, experiments, group discussions, and projects done in small groups. Adding more, this finding is also in relation to the view of Amin et al. (2013) that satisfying the learners through effective performance and quality measures teacher's teaching quality.

Table 1. Summary of Teachers' Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills in Carmen District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Online Connections	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Student Self-Perception	3.47	Extensive
Experience with Online Courses	3.43	Extensive
Instructor Evaluation	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.36	Moderately Extensive

3.1.1. *Online Connections*—In particular, this dimension has a category mean of 3.26 interpreted as moderately extensive which means that in terms of online connections, the teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills is sometimes observed in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. The mean ratings of the items range from 2.54 to 3.81. The item, Online connections is

useful in finding latest information about the school reflects a mean rating of 2.54 described as less extensive and interpreted as seldom observed. Meanwhile, the item Online connectivity contributes to the improvement of my interest in learning a mean rating of 3.81, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed in Carmen District, Davao del Norte.

The result implies that the instructiveness on online learning is sometimes observed by the respondents. This finding is congruent to the view of Hosseini and Kamal (2012) that online interactions include the the ability of individuals to troubleshoot when problems related to technical issues arise. Also, the result showed that the teachers perceived that internet usage data skills could be related to effective management and maintaining the condition of high-and-low technologies including ICT such as wireless broadband, dial-up internet connection, creating digital photos and videos, hardware and software programs, and the management of interactive whiteboards, blackboards, etc. This result is congruent to the view of Baran et al. (2011).

3.1.2. Students' Self-Perception—With respect to student self-perception, it reflects a category mean of 3.47 described as extensive which is interpreted as teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills is oftentimes observed. It can be seen that the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.66 to 4.01. The item, Motivating students who show low interest in school work has a mean rating of 2.66, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed among the respondents. Whereas, the item Helping students to think critically has a mean of 4.01 described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed. The result means that the ability to encourage students to learn and be involved in the educative process is oftentimes observed. This finding supports the view of Fredricks (2014) that enhancing students' self-perception involves teaching students the importance of working together to accomplish an instructional goal. A content-centered approach has a common theme in a classroom environment, in comparison to student-centered instruction. Adding more, the result supports the view of Kalaivani and Rajeswar (2016) self-perception is the students' view of his or her academic ability or academic characteristics in comparison with other

students. According to Izuchi and Onyekuru (2017) self-perception develops from consistent academic successes or failures over a period of time especially at formative stage of children's development.

3.1.3. Experience with Online Courses—With respect to experience with online courses, it reflects a category mean of 3.43 described as extensive which is interpreted as teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills is oftentimes observed. It can be seen that the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.14 to 3.85. The item, Using internet to communicate with the learners has a mean rating of 3.14, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. Whereas, the item Increasing the quality of my work has a mean of 3.85 described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed. The result means that student's ability to monitor their own phase of learning through the use of online connections is oftentimes observed. This finding supports the view of Shaukenova (2016) that the ability of an educator to use internet technology and other ICT related devices improves positive attitude of the students towards the use of technology because it help organize the students by helping them to gain thoughtful understanding and to familiarize themselves with several educational resource, approaches to evaluating and providing solutions to problems through research works, philosophies, creative activities and tests. The finding supports the view of Abedalaziz et al. (2013) pointed out that an ICT mediated classroom environment influence students' positive attitude towards technology usage.

3.1.4. Instructor Evaluation—This dimension has a category mean of 3.29 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as teachers' learner-centered pedagogical skills is sometimes observed. Looking at the mean ratings of the different items, they range from 2.65 to 4.02. The item, Performance assessment takes enough

time reflects a mean rating of 2.65, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes observed. The items, Believing that I extremely forced with performance tasks acquired a mean rating of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as item is oftentimes observed. The result implies that attitude on a performance assessment tool that was being used in the class is sometimes observed by the teachers. The result emphasizes that the teachers' attitude on a performance assessment tool that was being used in the class is oftentimes observed. The result is consistent to the findings of Jorge (2013) that performance assessment helps students develop some skills such as inquiry, problem-solving, oral presentation, organizing skills, and writing. Besides, performance assessment is so important that students' math process, higher-level thinking, problem-solving

skills were developed.

3.2. *Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes*—Table 2 reveals the summary on the extent of students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. As shown in the table, students' knowledge acquisition processes obtained an overall mean score of 4.01 with a descriptive rating of extensive. This means that students' knowledge acquisition processes is oftentimes manifested. Moreover, the students' knowledge acquisition processes in terms of mastery of the lesson acquired the highest mean score of 3.68 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. Meanwhile, students' knowledge acquisition processes in terms of classroom engagement acquired the lowest mean score of 3.35 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested.

Table 2. Summary on Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Mastery of the Lesson	3.68	Extensive
Communication	3.60	Extensive
Instructional Delivery	3.47	Extensive
Classroom Engagement	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.53	Extensive

This finding agrees with the view of Altındağ and Senemoğlu (2013) that characteristics such as an individual's acquisition of problem-solving competency, and experience the inquiry activity, stimulate their own thinking and help individuals find the relevance of subject matter with daily life, this is because when people acquire these skills, it allows students to be aware of what an individual knows and does not know, thus, developing their abilities to apply appropriate motivated strategies for learning basic livelihood skills. Likewise, the findings agree with Albalate et al. (2018) that

learners who are actively engaged in learning are efficient in using cognitive and metacognitive strategies. As Hubert (2017) noted, highly motivated learners can control various mental strategies for better cognitive performance and can concentrate over a period of time, easily learn new information and skills.

3.2.1. *Mastery of the Lesson*—Consequently, the dimension on mastery of the lesson as shown on Table 2 is described as extensive with a category mean of 3.68. This means that the knowledge acquisition processes of the TLE students in terms of mastery of the lesson is

oftentimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.23 to 3.87. The item, Doing their to reach the academic standards that I set for myself reflects a mean rating of 3.23, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as this item sometimes manifested. Further, the item Doing difficult academic tasks in which they believe they can succeed has a mean rating of 3.87, described as extensive, interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. The result shows that the students' ability to exert best effort to reach the academic standards that they set for themselves is oftentimes manifested. This finding is congruent to the view of Eryılmaz et al. (2011) that students who have desire for learning are those students who have motivation for effective participation. This result is congruent to the idea of Lee and Reeve (2012) that motivation in the school environment is a process for the students to initiate and execute the class activity. The motivating processes that strengthen and sustain the classroom activities of the students are multi-dimensional and include the needs, expectations or beliefs and goals of the students.

3.2.2. Communication—This domain as shown in Table 2 has a category mean of 3.60, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain of students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte is oftentimes manifested. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.36 to 3.91. Specifically, the item, being able to present main ideas of the topic at the beginning of the class a mean rating of 3.36, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. The item, Beginning the learning situations by communicating to other learners reflects a mean rating of 3.91 described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. This means that the process of communicating techniques essential for acquiring, processing, storing, and recalling in-

formation in a certain situation is oftentimes manifested. The result is similar to the findings of the study conducted by Francois (2016) that communication is the successfully directed – performance plans, or producing systems that aim at decreasing the turbulence that could exist between the existing knowledge of a learner and the objectives he wants to achieve. These strategies include a set of activities that help in choosing the proper information, connecting the newly acquired information with the previously stored one, and creating a positive learning environment and maintain it. The result is parallel to the view of Suyitno (2017) communication in its simplest form as the use of the mind (cognition) to solve a problem or complete a task.

3.2.3. Instructional Delivery—This particular domain of knowledge acquisition processes of the learners, as shown in Table 2 reflects an extensive category mean of 3.47 which means that it is oftentimes manifested. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.24 to 3.67. The table further reveals that the item Crafting good questions has a mean rating of 3.24, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Adjusting to the lessons reflects a mean rating of 3.67, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. This means that the instructional activities that will be carried out in the instructional process and which instructional methods and techniques that will be employed in the process is oftentimes manifested. The result agrees with the view of Llego (2017) that effective instructional delivery strategies manifest student-centered classroom management approach. In a student-centered learning environment, the teacher gets to know their learners, share their ideas and their management approaches allow them and their pupil to see one another as people.

3.2.4. Classroom Engagement—Knowledge acquisition processes of the learners in terms of classroom engagement acquires mod-

erately extensive category mean of 3.35 which means that it is sometimes manifested. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.13 to 3.54. The table further reveals that the item Talking about class topics outside of class has a mean rating of 3.13, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Completing homework on time reflects a mean rating of 3.54, described as extensive, interpreted as item oftentimes manifested. The result implies that the students' involvement in the scientific activity of the classroom and their commitment to learning the learning content is oftentimes manifested. This result is similar to the view of Finn and Zimmer (2013) that student engagement as the working time in which students are fully involved in an academic task or plan related to the learning process. The result agrees with Ayub et al. (2016) that engagement in schoolwork involved both learners' behaviors and attitudes, therefore, engaged students would seek out activities either inside or outside the classroom that would lead them to be successful in their learning.

3.3. Relationship Between Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte—The results of the analysis on the relationship between learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte, are presented. Bivariate correlation

3.4. Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Extents of Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte—Table 4 presents the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating on learner-centered pedagogical skills, and the extensive rating on stu-

analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned. Meanwhile, Table 3 shows that the learner-centered pedagogical skills of teachers have a significant positive relationship with the student's knowledge acquisition processes with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .742$, $p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the learner-centered pedagogical skills changes, students' knowledge acquisition processes also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte. The finding supports the proposition of Christian et al. (2011) that the learner-centered teaching skills of the teachers can be a motivation concept that could lead to the voluntary allocation of personal resources directed at the range of tasks demanded in the teaching profession. Likewise, the result also agrees with the view of Karatas and Gules (2014) that these teachers give everything for organizations goals, they tend to show quality performance in teaching, they take responsibilities for the students, and they make an effort and spend time time as needed. In addition, the result is in line with the idea of Sword (2021) that individuals who know about the different kinds of strategies for learning, thinking, and problem solving will be more likely to use them.

students' knowledge acquisition processes. On the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating of learner-centered pedagogical skills, there were three emerging codes that identified namely: student engagement and motivation; personalization; and technology integration.

3.4.1. Student Engagement and Motivation—When teachers employ learner centered

Table 3. Relationship Between Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Online Connections	0.411**	0.000	Reject H0
Student Self-Perception	0.526**	0.000	Reject H0
Experience with Online Courses	0.229**	0.001	Reject H0
Instructor Evaluation	0.279**	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills	0.554**	0.000	Reject H0

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 < r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 < r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.0 < r < 0.3$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$

pedagogical skills that promote student engagement and motivation, learners are more likely to acquire a deeper understanding of the subject matter. This can result in improved academic performance and retention of knowledge.

The result denotes the abilities and approaches of teachers to design and implement instructional methods that prioritize the needs, interests, and preferences of individual learners. Students who are engaged and motivated are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward learning. They may view education as a meaningful and enjoyable process, fostering a lifelong love of learning. This supports the idea of Shehadeh (2012) that learner-centered approaches encourage active participation, which can lead to richer class discussions, collaborative projects, and a more inclusive classroom atmosphere where every student feels valued and heard.

3.4.2. *Personalization*—This involves recognizing that each learner is distinct and requires a customized approach to maximize their learning potential. Teachers with strong learner-centered pedagogical skills in personalization prioritize building a learning environ-

ment where students feel valued, supported, and empowered to take an active role in their education. The result implies that personalization can lead to better academic achievement because instruction is aligned with individual students' readiness levels and abilities. When content and pace are matched to students' needs, they are more likely to grasp and retain knowledge effectively. Personalized learning experiences tend to be more engaging for students. When they see the relevance of what they are learning to their own lives and interests, they become more motivated and invested in their studies. This is congruent to the view of Jalbani (2014) that personalization can boost students' confidence and self-efficacy because it empowers them to make choices about their learning. When students see that their preferences and abilities are considered, they are more likely to believe in their capacity to succeed.

3.4.3. *Technology Integration*—Teachers with strong learner-centered pedagogical skills in technology integration incorporate digital technologies in ways that empower students, personalize learning, and promote active engagement. This approach recognizes that tech-

nology can be a powerful tool to create a more student-centered and interactive learning environment.

The result underscores the role of technology in making learning more engaging. By incorporating multimedia elements, interactive simulations, and gamified activities, technology can enhance student engagement, leading to improved retention of knowledge and a greater enthusiasm for learning. This finding supports the view of Amin et al. (2013) that technology can be used by teachers to tailor instruction to individual students' needs, enabling differentiated learning paths, adaptive assessments, and personalized feedback. This personalization can help students progress at their own pace and address their unique learning challenges. Importantly, technology can provide accessible learning materials and resources for students with diverse needs, and facilitate the use of assistive technologies, such as screen readers or speech recognition software, to support students with disabilities. The participants' standpoints on the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating of students' knowledge acquisition processes identified three emerging codes: effective use of resources, self-directed learning, and prior knowledge and background.

3.4.4. Effective Use of Resources—Effective resource use in students' knowledge acquisition processes involves making informed decisions about resource selection and implementation to enhance learning outcomes, engagement, and equity in education. It empowers students with the skills they need to become lifelong learners and contributes to improving educational practices.

The result implies that when resources are effectively used, students are more likely to achieve higher levels of understanding and mastery of the subject matter. They are better equipped to meet educational objectives and perform well in assessments. The result agrees with the view of Albalate, Larcia, and Jaen

(2018) that extensive resource utilization can lead to increased student engagement and motivation. Well-designed resources, such as interactive learning materials or real-world applications, can make learning more interesting and relevant, keeping students motivated to explore and learn. Effective resource use allows educators to tailor their teaching methods to individual students' needs and learning styles. This promotes personalized learning experiences that cater to diverse abilities and preferences.

3.4.5. Self-Directed Learning—Extensive self-directed learning empowers students to take control of their own educational journey, resulting in increased motivation, autonomy, adaptability, and the development of essential skills. This approach not only enhances the learning process but also prepares individuals for a lifetime of self-directed and independent learning.

The result implies that self-directed learners are often more motivated and engaged because they have control over their learning experiences. They can choose topics that genuinely interest them, making learning more intrinsically motivating. Extensive self-directed learning encourage learners to take ownership of their education. This sense of ownership can lead to greater commitment and a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The result supports the findings of Otoo, Iddrisu, Kessie, and Larbi (2018) that self-directed learning fosters a mindset of lifelong learning. Individuals who become adept at self-directed learning are more likely to continue learning throughout their lives, keeping their knowledge and skills up to date.

3.4.6. Prior Knowledge and Background—Extensive prior knowledge and background play a significant role in students' knowledge acquisition processes. Leveraging and building upon this existing knowledge can lead to more effective learning experiences, improved problem-solving and critical thinking skills, increased motivation, and a more inclusive educational

environment. Recognizing and addressing individual differences in prior knowledge can contribute to a more tailored and supportive educational experience for all students.

This means that extensive prior knowledge provides students with a solid foundation upon which they can build new knowledge. When students can connect new information to what they already know, learning becomes more meaningful and efficient. The result agrees with the view

of Hubert (2017) that students with extensive prior knowledge in a particular area often find it easier to acquire related knowledge. They can quickly grasp complex concepts and integrate new information into their existing mental frameworks. A rich background in a subject area enhances students' problem-solving abilities. They can draw upon their existing knowledge to solve novel problems and make connections between different concepts.

Table 4. Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Extents of Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte

Essential Theme	Reasons
Confirmed Moderately Extensive Rating on Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills	Student Engagement and Motivation Personalization Technology Integration
Confirmed Extensive Rating on Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes	Effective Use of Resources Self-Directed Learning Prior Knowledge and Background

3.5. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students' Knowledge Acquisition Processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte*—Table 5 presents the participants' standpoints on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between learner-centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes. Three emerging codes were identified: autonomy and responsibility, individualized learning, and life-long learning.

3.5.1. *Autonomy and Responsibility*—Autonomy and responsibility are key components of learner-centered pedagogical skills signifi-

cantly impacting students' knowledge acquisition processes. These skills foster motivation, ownership, critical thinking, self-direction, and accountability, preparing students for success in both their educational journey and real-life endeavors.

The result implies that when students have the autonomy to make choices about their learning and take responsibility for their education, they become more motivated and engaged in the learning process. They feel a sense of ownership, which drives their desire to acquire knowledge. The result supports the findings of Tasgin and Tunc (2018) that autonomy and responsibility foster a sense of ownership over one's learn-

ing journey. Students feel they are active participants in their education rather than passive recipients of information. This ownership encourages them to take their studies more seriously. Autonomy encourages students to think critically and decide what and how they learn. Responsibility for their learning process requires them to solve problems and make choices, leading to the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

3.5.2. Individualized Learning—Individualized learning, as a component of learner-centered pedagogical skills, fosters tailored, engaging, and practical knowledge acquisition processes. It supports students in becoming more self-directed, motivated, and adaptable learners, preparing them for success in their educational endeavors and beyond.

This implies that individualized learning recognizes and accommodates each student's unique learning needs and preferences. This tailoring of educational experiences ensures that students can acquire knowledge in a way that best suits their abilities and learning styles. The result agrees with the view of Parr (2011) that when students have a say in how they learn, they are more likely to be engaged in the educational process. This engagement enhances their motivation to acquire knowledge because they find the learning experiences relevant and personally meaningful. Individualized learning allows students to delve deeper into subjects that are most interesting. This depth of exploration leads to a deeper understanding of the material and better

knowledge retention.

3.5.3. Self-Directed Learning—Self-directed learning, as a component of learner-centered pedagogical skills, empowers students to take control of their educational journey. It enhances motivation, autonomy, critical thinking, adaptability, and the development of essential lifelong learning skills. Self-directed learning prepares students for academic success and a lifetime of independent and self-directed learning.

The result suggests that self-directed learning places learners in control of their education. Self-directed learning, or student-directed learning, is an educational theory or content delivery method in which students take control of their education. Through self-directed learning, students set their own goals and deadlines while following a broad assignment outcome. Students take ownership of their learning experiences, which makes them more invested and motivated to acquire knowledge. The result supports the idea of Benken et al. (2015) that self-directed learning fosters autonomy, as students have the freedom to choose what, when, and how they learn. This autonomy is coupled with a sense of responsibility, as students understand that their progress depends on their efforts. When students have a say in their learning process, they are more likely to be intrinsically motivated. Their motivation comes from a genuine interest in the subject rather than external factors like grades or rewards.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the influence of learner-centered pedagogical skills on the students' knowledge acquisition

processes using mixed methods specifically the sequential-explanatory design wherein adapted survey questionnaires will be used in the quan-

Table 5. Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students’ Knowledge Acquisition Processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte

Essential Theme	Reasons
Confirmed Significant Relationship Between Learner-Centered Pedagogical Skills and Students’ Knowledge Acquisition Processes	Autonomy and Responsibility
	Individualized Learning
	Lifelong Learning

titative phase and through in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD) in the qualitative phase. On one hand, in the quantitative phase of the study, adapted survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the teachers of public elementary schools, to determine the significance of the influence of learner-centered pedagogical skills on the students’ knowledge acquisition processes. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument.

Based on the results the summary of the findings were the following: Learner-centered pedagogical skills in Carmen District, Davao del Norte has an overall mean of 3.36 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. Meanwhile, learner-centered pedagogical skills in terms of online connections, student self-perception, experience with online courses, and instructor evaluation obtained the mean scores of 3.26, 3.47, 3.43, and 3.29, respectively. Students’ knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte has an overall mean of 3.53 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, students’ knowledge acquisition processes in terms of mastery of the lesson, communication, instructional delivery, and classroom engagement obtained the mean scores of 3.68, 3.60, 3.47, and 3.35, respectively. The result showed

that learner-centered pedagogical skills has a significant positive relationship with the students’ knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .554, p < 0.05$). On the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating on learner-centered pedagogical skills in Carmen District, Davao del Norte, the three emerging codes are as follows: student engagement and motivation; personalization; and technology integration. On the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the extensive rating on students’ knowledge acquisition processes, the three emerging codes are as follows: effective use of resources; self-directed learning; and prior knowledge and background. On standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between learner-centered pedagogical skills and students’ knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte, the three emerging codes are as follows: autonomy and responsibility; individualized learning; and lifelong learning.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as survey questionnaire and number of participants), several conclusions are generated: Learner-centered pedagogical skills in Carmen District, Davao del Norte was de-

scribed as extensive. On one hand, learner-centered pedagogical skills in terms of student self-perception and experience with online courses belongs to extensive rating. On the other hand, learner-centered pedagogical skills in terms of online connections and instructor evaluation belongs to moderately extensive rating. The result denotes that the measurement of teacher's skills, performance and beliefs that reflect real-world situations and require the students to develop their original responses explaining the processes followed in order to achieve those results is sometimes observed among the teachers. Students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte acquired an extensive rating. On one hand, students' knowledge acquisition processes in terms of mastery of the lesson, communication, and instructional delivery belongs to extensive rating. On the other hand, students' knowledge acquisition processes in terms of classroom engagement acquired moderately extensive rating. This indicates that individual's acquisition of problem-solving competency, experience the inquiry activity, stimulate their own thinking and help individuals find the relevance of subject matter with daily life, this is because when people acquired these skills, it allows students to be aware of what an individual knows and does not know, thus, developing their abilities to apply appropriate motivated strategies for learning basic livelihood skills. The result showed that learner-centered pedagogical skills has a significant positive relationship with students' knowledge acquisition processes. This implies that learner-centered teaching skills of the teachers can be a motivation concept that could lead to the voluntary allocation of personal resources directed at the range of tasks demanded in the teaching profession. The quantitative results on the moderately extensive learner-centered pedagogical skills in Carmen District, Davao del Norte were further substantiated by codes (student engagement and motivation; personaliza-

tion; and technology integration) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the extensive students' knowledge acquisition processes were further substantiated by codes (effective use of resources; self-directed learning; and prior knowledge and background) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the significant relationship between learner centered pedagogical skills and students' knowledge acquisition processes in Carmen District, Davao del Norte were further substantiated by codes (autonomy and responsibility; individualized learning; and lifelong learning) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The salient quantitative and qualitative findings revealed a parallel result. The corroborated finding means that the quantitative and qualitative findings merged and connected.

4.3. Recommendations—The researcher recommends that school administrators may endeavor to provide public elementary teachers with seminar workshop in order to give the teachers adequate background and knowledge, and usable information to improve their teaching confidence. Confident teacher would have a positive impact on his or her students' achievement, attitude, affective and even socio-emotional growth. To improve the schooling experience of low progress learners, enhancing teachers' beliefs in their teaching competence may be a viable approach. Further, teachers should take time to reflect on their practice and pull out the positives. Reflecting would help to overcome negative self-perceptions and recognise the strengths in the classroom. By reflecting on their teaching strengths and celebrating them, teachers could build sense of self-worth

and belief, which ultimately leads to confidence. Furthermore, since the result revealed an R2 of 0.342, and it implies that 34.20 percent of the variation can be attributed to other variables or factors not covered in the study; it is recommended that a mediating analysis on the factors that influenced the knowledge acquisition processes of the learners in public elementary schools in larger context should be conducted.

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